

COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF BI-POSITIVE SILVER WITH PYRIDINE
CARBOXYLIC ACIDS. PART I. ARGENTIC
NICOTINATE AND *iso*NICOTINATE

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Complex compounds of bi-positive silver with nicotinic and *isonicotinic* acids have been prepared in the form of cinnamon-red crystals by the action of potassium persulphate on silver nitrate and the organic ligand in aqueous medium. The compounds are paramagnetic with $\mu_n = 1.73$ Bohr (approx.). A study of the X-ray diffraction of the crystals of Ag^{II} - and Cu^{II} -*isonicotinates* furnishes evidence in support of their isomorphous character.

It is suggested that the configuration of the complexes is best represented by assuming that their molecules are either dimeric, or polymeric with the formation of an unending two dimensional sheets or layers. They are to be regarded as inner-metallic penetration complexes with planar dsp^2 hybrid bonds.

Bi-positive silver is known to form a very stable chelate complex of the inner-metallic type with pyridine-2-carboxylic acid (picolinic acid). This was first studied by Barbieri (*Atti Accad. Lincei*, 1933, 17, 1078) and was found by Cox, Wardlaw and Webster (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 775) to be isomorphous with copper picolinate. Burada (*Ann. Sci. Univ. Jassy*, 1935, 20, 71) also reported the preparation of a red crystalline bi-positive silver complex of quinolinic acid (pyridine-2:3-dicarboxylic acid). In both these acids, the functional groups $-N$ and $-COOH$ are in very favourable positions to give rise to stable five-membered chelate rings by co-ordination with the silver (II) atom. With a view to studying whether these functional groups at other positions of the pyridine ring can at all lead to the formation of any inner-metallic complexes with bi-positive silver, a systematic investigation with all the available mono-, di- and tri-carboxylic acids of pyridine was considered desirable. A preliminary qualitative examination with nicotinic acid (pyridine-3-carboxylic acid), *isonicotinic* acid (pyridine-4-carboxylic acid) and cinchomeric acid (pyridine-3:4-dicarboxylic acid) gave very promising results. In the present communication argentic complexes of pyridine monocarboxylic acids, nicotinic and *isonicotinic* acids have been described. Both nicotinic and *isonicotinic* acids, on being treated with silver nitrate and potassium persulphate solution, furnished insoluble cinnamon-red crystalline complexes with a paramagnetic moment ($\mu_n = 1.73 \mu_B$), corresponding to the presence of one unpaired electron, characteristic of bi-positive silver. Of these, argentic *isonicotinate* has been found to be isomorphous with the corresponding cupric compound from an X-ray study of their powdered crystals. A similar examination of the nicotinate complexes (Chackrabarty and Banerjee, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1955, 29, 357) also indicates a general resemblance between the argentic and cupric compounds, though no definite statement can be made about their isomorphous character.

The structures of these argentic complexes present a rather intriguing problem. Their properties indicate that they should be viewed as inner-metallic penetration complexes with planar dsp^2 hybrid bonds. Both show the same composition $\text{Ag}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{O}_2\text{N})_2$:

On the basis of these simple structures, 1:3 or *meta* positions in the nicotinate and 1:4 or *para* positions in the isonicotinate complex are to be bridged by the silver atom with formation of 6- and 7-membered chelate rings, which are rather improbable and are unknown in the case of organic compounds. But the possibility of the *meta* positions of nicotinic acid being bridged by the silver atom cannot be altogether excluded in view of a very large single-bond covalent radius (1.53 Å) of the silver atom, which is almost twice that of carbon (0.77 Å). But such an interpretation cannot be seriously entertained in the case of isonicotinic acid, where the *para* positions have to be bridged. Plausible configurations for these complexes can, however, be represented by assuming that their molecules are either dimeric as in (I), or polymeric as in (II) with the formation of an unending two-dimensional sheets or layers. The silver atoms in these molecules occupy the centre of a square, being co-ordinated with N- and O- atoms of the acids in one plane.

It can therefore be stated that all the three pyridine monocarboxylic acids (α , β and γ) afford bi-positive chelate silver complexes of the inner-metallic type with similar properties.

EXPERIMENTAL

Argentio Nicotinate.—Nicotinic acid (3 g.) was dissolved in 50 c.c. of water (if necessary by heating) and mixed at the room temperature with a solution of silver

nitrate (1.36 g. in 10 c.c.) when silver (I) nicotinate separated as a precipitate. A solution of potassium persulphate (6 g. in the minimum quantity of water) was afterwards added dropwise to this mixture with constant stirring. The stirring was continued for about three hours by means of a magnetic stirrer in the cold. A chocolate-red crystalline powder formed the final product. This was filtered through a sintered-glass bed, washed with cold water till free from sulphate, and then dried in a vacuum desiccator over CaCl_2 ; yield 3.5 g.

The substance forms brick-red, fine, needle-shaped prismatic crystals, insoluble in water, but readily decomposes in dilute mineral acids or alkalis. With cold dilute acetic acid also it suffers decomposition on warming. The substance can be heated to 115° without any appreciable decomposition. It remains unchanged, when kept dry, for months. $\mu_{10} = 1.74$. From an acid solution of potassium iodide it immediately liberates iodine. [Found: Ag (oxidimetric), 30.2; Ag (gravimetric as AgCl), 30.4; N, 8.1. $\text{Ag}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2)_2$ requires Ag, 30.68; N, 7.95 per cent].

Tables I and II summarise the results of measurement on the X-ray pictures of copper and silver complexes of isonicotinic acid.

TABLE I

Copper isonicotinate.

θ .	Visual intensity.	d .	θ .	Visual intensity.	d .	θ .	Visual intensity.	d .
$5^\circ 27'$	v.s.	$8.10\text{\AA}$	$13^\circ 54'$	w.	$3.21\text{\AA}$	$20^\circ 12'$	w.	$2.23\text{\AA}$
$7^\circ 10'$	w.	6.17	$14^\circ 37'$	w.	3.05	$21^\circ 21'$	m.	2.11
$9^\circ 45'$	m.	4.55	$15^\circ 11'$	w.	2.94	$22^\circ 30'$	w.	2.01
$11^\circ 02'$	s.	4.02	$16^\circ 20'$	w.	2.74	$23^\circ 56'$	w.	1.90
$11^\circ 54'$	m.	3.74	$16^\circ 54'$	w.	2.65	$24^\circ 30'$	w.	1.86
$12^\circ 53'$	w.	3.45	$18^\circ 55'$	w.	2.37	$26^\circ 39'$	w.	1.72

TABLE II

Silver^(m) isonicotinate.

θ .	Visual intensity.	d .	θ .	Visual intensity.	d .	θ .	Visual intensity.	d .
$5^\circ 27'$	v.s.	$8.10\text{\AA}$	$14^\circ 02'$	w.	$3.18\text{\AA}$	$17^\circ 20'$	w.	$2.58\text{\AA}$
$7^\circ 10'$	w.	6.17	$15^\circ 02'$	w.	2.97	$18^\circ 46'$	w.	2.39
$9^\circ 53'$	m.	4.49	$16^\circ 02'$	w.	2.79	$20^\circ 55'$	m.	2.16
$10^\circ 53'$	s.	4.08	$16^\circ 37'$	w.	2.69	$22^\circ 13'$	m.	2.04
$12^\circ 02'$	s.	3.69				$23^\circ 47'$	w.	1.91

Argentico isonicotinate.—isonicotinic acid (1.87 g.) was dissolved in 100 c.c. of boiling water and treated with a solution of silver nitrate (0.87 g. in 5 c.c.). On cooling, silver (I) isonicotinate separated as a fine precipitate. The mixture was then

treated dropwise with constant stirring with a solution of sodium persulphate (3 g.) in the least quantity of water. The stirring was continued with the help of a magnetic stirrer for about 4 hours in the cold, when the white silver (I) isonicotinate was completely converted into cinnamon-red crystals of the bi-positive silver complex. The crystals were filtered, washed and dried as in the previous case; yield 1.5 g.

Argentio isonicotinate resembles the corresponding nicotinate complex more or less closely in all its properties. $\mu_n = 1.60$. [Found: Ag, 30.6 (oxidimetric), 30.8 (gravimetric); C, 41.52. Ag ($C_6H_4NO_2$)₂ requires Ag, 30.7; C, 40.9 per cent].

The powder X-ray photograph of the substance as well as of the corresponding copper isonicotinate, $Cu(C_6H_4NO_2)_2$, were taken in a cylindrical camera of radius 5.0 cm. by using copper radiation from a Hadding tube run at a voltage of 40. kv. with a tube current of 15 ma. [cf. Fig. 3 (a and b)]. Fig. 4 (a and b) shows the powder photograph of copper and silver complexes of nicotinic acid.

It is evident from the tables that the d values and also the intensity of the corresponding powder lines of the two isonicotinate complexes are almost identical, indicating their structural similarity.

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